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Formalization of Syntax and Semantics of Ontology Languages in Biology

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Introduction

The **Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory** is the oldest federal research institution of the United States of America, located in Berkeley, California. While originally focusing its activities on Nuclear Physics as a host to the cyclotron developed by Ernest O. Lawrence^[1], the LBNL now shelters a dozen of departments ranging from computational research and systems biology to materials sciences.

Part of the Environmental Genomics and Systems Biology division, the **Berkeley Bioinformatics Open-source Projects** is a team of developers and researchers participating to numerous initiatives in the bioinformatics community, such as the Gene Ontology Consortium^[2], the Monarch Initiative^[3] or the Alliance of Genome Resources^a. With seven full-time members working on both infrastructural and experimental projects, the BBOP team focuses on the development, use and integration of ontologies into biological and biomedical analyses. Furthermore, the BBOP server hosts some legacy ontologies that are critical to the whole ontology ecosystem, as well as being in charge of the maintenance of the OBO Foundry^[4].

Ontologies are structures used to describe knowledge in a formal way, by defining entities and the relationships between them. Originally developed by logicians, they became widespread in the bioinformatics community thanks to projects such as the Gene Ontology or ChEBI^[5], an ontology of chemicals with biological relevance. Although most scientists use them as controlled vocabularies for data repositories or data formats, ontologies are much more powerful, benefiting from results of the description logic theory. In particular, *reasoners* – programs that can infer consequences from ontology assertions – open the way for more in-depth analyses.

GO was started in 1998, much before the first specification of the **Ontology Web Language**^[6], which is the language developed and recommended by the W3C to store ontological knowledge. Consequently, GO as well as GO-derived projects started using an *ad-hoc*, frame-based format now known as the **Open Biomedical Ontologies** language. The standardisation of the OBO language only became effective with the release of the version 1.0^b specification in 2004. However, because it had to take into account these numerous existing ontologies, the format in itself was poorly constrained, and the translation into OWL was still not entirely possible.

a <https://www.alliancegenome.org/>

b https://owlcollab.github.io/oboformat/doc/GO.format.obo-1_0.html

While not normative yet, the 1.2 format that released in 2006 was much more specified, opening the door to translation efforts such as the ones of **Golbreich et al.**^[7] for OWL1.1 in 2007 and then of **Tirmizi et al.**^[8] for OWL2 in 2009. All these proposed semantic mappings had in common the restriction of OBO clauses into a small set that fit the *SHOIN* description logic, expressible with the OWL-DL language. Therefore started the work on the OBO format version 1.4, which is the latest and yet unreleased version of the OBO language, in order to guarantee OWL2 expressivity of OBO ontologies, at the cost of additional syntax restrictions.

However, because it is currently the only implementation of the OBO format, the **OWL API**^[9] and its behaviour have become the *de-facto* standard of multiple ontology projects, both on the development side and on the consumption side. After trying to write a formal OBO parser for the pronto Python library, as well as limited OWL to OBO mappings, I realised how essential a correct implementation of the OBO standard was, and ultimately contacted Dr. Mungall with the following goals in mind: fixing the OBO format version 1.4 in the short term, and providing a correct stack for OBO, independent from the OWL API, in the long-term.

Results

OBO 1.4 Syntax and Semantics

Grammar

The OBO format version 1.4 provides a BNF grammar^a that highly contrasts with the previous versions of the format: clauses are now part of the syntax, and the value of each clause is also – at least partially – syntactically validated. However, at the time I joined the BBOP team, the grammar was still ambiguous and had missing declarations, such as the nonexistent `SynonymType-ID` rule. I contributed to the working draft of the specification by refactoring some of the common rules, while also adding patches to prevent ambiguity, such as the synonym rule presented in Eq.1. A comprehensive list of edits can be found in the Git history of the `owlcollab/oboformat` repository^b. I was assisted to check the ambiguity of the grammar with the `pest` library I used to derive the tokenizer (see *OBO Parser Implementation* section).

- a. `syn ::= synonym-Tag QuotedString ws SynonymScope [ws SynonymType-ID] XrefList`
- b. `synonym: "chemical entity" EXACT [UniProt]`

Equation 1: **a.** Definition of the production rule for synonym clauses in BNF syntax.
b. Example of an ambiguous synonym clause, where `[UniProt]` could be interpreted both as a `SynonymType-ID` or as an `XrefList`. This was fixed by preventing synonym types identifiers from beginning with a square bracket.

Chris Mungall and I also agreed on some breaking changes, such as relaxing the production rule of the `created_by` clause to allow free text in lieu of an identifier, as the translation was going to produce an OWL Literal in any case. This allows authors to put their complete name (such as “Martin Larraalde”) in `created_by` clauses instead of identifiers (such as “Martin_Larraalde” or “ORCID:0000-0002-3947-4444”) to accommodate some existing ontology projects like UBERON^[10], although it goes against the GO recommended practices. Some other breaking changes, such as requiring quoted strings on all `property_value` clauses, were stripped because they did not bring any sufficient improvement and would have ended slowing the adoption of the new format.

a <http://owllcollab.github.io/oboformat/doc/obo-syntax.html#3>

b <https://github.com/owllcollab/oboformat/commits/gh-pages>

Semantics

The translation of some metadata clauses such as `created_by` was changed to use the Dublin Core elements^[11], while some others were updated to refer to proper entities of the `oboInOwl` controlled vocabulary (e.g. the translation of `xrefs` into annotation properties was changed to use the `oboInOwl:hasDbXref` annotation property instead of the undeclared `oboInOwl:xref` property).

OBO Parser Implementation

The improvements to the syntax were carried out by developing a formal parser implementation using an exact translation of the BNF grammar into a PEG grammar to be consumed by the `pest` library. This parser served two purposes: checking the formal rules in the OBO working draft, and validating the existing OBO ontologies against the new format.

- a. `QuotedString ::= ''' { (OBOChar - (''' — '!')) } '''`
- b. `QuotedString = @{ ''' ~ (''' ~ (!' — OboChar)) * ~ ''' }`

Equation 2: **a.** BNF and **b.** PEG grammar syntaxes for the `QuotedString` production rule. Note the braces do not have the same semantic value in both grammar languages: PEG uses them to group a definition while they are a repetition operator in BNF.

To comply with the modularity advised in the Rust ecosystem following the UNIX philosophy – and also to reduce compilation time, the parser was released in a single crate named `fastobo-syntax`, hosted on GitHub and available to download on the `crates.io` website^a under the MIT license.

OBO Syntax Tree

In order to further edit OBO documents, and to explore them between the syntactic and semantic levels, I developed an AST for the OBO language. Since it relies on the OBO 1.4 format version, it is currently the only library available for syntax edition of OBO documents.

The OBO format also define particular macros in its header that can be used to factor some common declarations, such as the `default_namespace` clause, or all the `treat_xrefs` macros such as the one presented in List.1 that can transform simple cross-references in a frame into more refined clauses. These macros have been implemented as methods on the `OboDocument` struct so that end users can resolve them easily before consuming an OBO ontology.

a <https://crates.io/crates/fastobo-syntax>

a.

```
treat-xrefs-as-genus-differentia: TEST part_of something
```

```
[Term]
```

```
id: TEST:001
```

```
xref: TEST:002
```

```
[Term]
```

```
id: TEST:002
```

b.

```
treat-xrefs-as-genus-differentia: TEST part_of something
```

```
[Term]
```

```
id: TEST:001
```

```
xref: TEST:002
```

```
intersection_of: TEST:002
```

```
intersection_of: part_of something
```

```
[Term]
```

```
id: TEST:002
```

Listing 1: **a.** A small test ontology composed of two term frames. **b.** The equivalent ontology after the `treat-xrefs` macro is applied to the whole document. This kind of macros is often found in older ontologies developed with OboEdit that did not allow `intersection_of` clauses in plain term frames.

The AST supports the optional parts of an OBO document, such as the trailing qualifiers and end-line comments, and can also be serialized back into a canonical OBO document, meaning any canonical OBO document should roundtrip as expected.

I also implemented the Visitor design pattern^[12] for the syntax tree in the form of a `Visit` trait such as the ones found in various Rust AST libraries like `syn`^a. This pattern makes it possible to write simple scripts or snippets such as the ones used in the `fastobo-validator` binary, or in the library itself for syntactic transformations like the identifier compaction process.

The source code is hosted on GitHub and available to download as `fastobo` on the `crates.io` registry^b under the MIT license. It is continuously tested against most products of the OBO foundry, as well as against custom-made test cases to verify the correctness of the parser and of the serializer. Continuous integration is carried out by Travis-CI, with dependency management being monitored through Dependabot. Documentation for the latest version can be found on `docs.rs`.

a <https://docs.rs/syn/1.0.3/syn/visit/trait.Visit.html>

b <https://crates.io/crates/fastobo>

OBO Foundry Ecosystem Validation

State of the OBO Foundry

The OBO Foundry is the central repository for ontologies of the biomedical field that follow a set of good practices that ensure their compatibility with the OWL2 language and proper interoperability between the different ontologies it hosts. Out of the 143 projects released on the OBO Foundry, 69 provide an OBO product, either natively or using a conversion utility such as ROBOT^[13]. Using a simple library I developed^a to deserialize the JSON listings of the OBO Foundry, I tried to validate all the OBO products it stored. The results of this validation process can be found in Fig.1, grouped by conversion tool if any could be found.

This figure shows that there is no strict correlation between the OBO correctness and the conversion tool being used, which has two possible explanations: most conversion tools wrap the OWL API directly, and most conversion tools do not perform validation of the resulting OBO product, which can be invalid even starting from a valid OWL2 file. This can be the case for instance with string literals in OWL not being escaped as expected; this kind of error was encountered in the Cell Ontology^b for instance.

Figure 1: 1.4 compliance of ontologies released in OBO format on the OBO Foundry, grouped by conversion tool if they are obtained from an OWL source. OWL-only ontologies are provided for numerical reference. other encompasses some older conversion tools, such as the incomplete owl2obo XSLT script.

a <https://github.com/althonos/obofoundry.rs>

b <https://github.com/obophenotype/cell-ontology/pull/555>

Most of the 29 invalid OBO ontologies were so because of the breaking changes introduced by the 1.4 format, in particular with the additional constraints on xrefs, that were changed from free text to IRI-referenced entities. I contributed the fixes required to 13 of them, including CL^[14], ECO^[15] or BSPO^[16], and reported the errors to 9 additional ones that are still maintained. The overall progress is publicly available as a collaborative project in the FastOBO organisation on GitHub^a.

I also performed small sanity checks on ISBNs found in the Gene Ontology: this helped identifying 37 invalid ISBNs references^b out of the 249 ISBNs referenced in the Gene Ontology. We expect that with the additional constraints over cross-references in OBO documents, more and more errors like these will be identified in major OBO ontologies.

ODK Integration

As there was no standard tool for ontology project management for a long time, most ontologies ended up writing their own release pipeline. For OBO ontologies in particular, it was no rare to see UNIX commands being used to edit the document directly, at the cost of eventual invalid resulting files. The kickstart of the Ontology Development Kit^[17] helped streamlining the release process for less-knowledgeable ontology curators, but it could still produce – and ultimately release – invalid files.

To prevent this from happening, I developed a small utility using the `fastobo` library that can perform syntactic and simple semantic tests on an OBO file to verify its correctness. It helps identifying the errors by grouping the errors based on the frames they are part of. The current version can check for the OBO 1.4 syntax, for invalid cardinality of clauses, and for invalid ISBN cross-references. An example output on an erroneous OBO file from the PORO ontology^[18] can be found in Fig.2. The accent was put on simplicity of use, as well as proper explanations of any of the discovered errors.

Although included in the ODK^c, it is also available to download from source on `crates.io`^d, or as a built binary from Bintray^e. Linux releases in particular are compiled statically against the `musl libc`^[19] to allow the final binary to be ported to any recent Linux distribution, including Alpine Linux used in the ODK Docker image^[20].

a <https://github.com/orgs/fastobo/projects/2>

b <https://github.com/geneontology/go-ontology/issues/17190>

c <https://github.com/INCATools/ontology-development-kit/pull/215>

d <https://crates.io/crates/fastobo-validator>

e <https://bintray.com/fastobo/fastobo-validator/static>

```
/tmp fastobo-validator poro.obo Tue 23 Jul 2019 15:28:17 UTC
Parsing `poro.obo`
Finished parsing `poro.obo` in 0.03s
Failed validation of `poro.obo` (13 errors)
--> in frame adjacent_to
duplicate "def" clauses
--> in frame produced_by
duplicate "name" clauses
--> in frame continuous_with
duplicate "name" clauses
```

Figure 2: The output of fastobo-validator on poro.obo, which contains duplicate clauses, possibly because of an invalid OWL to OBO translation during its release process. The program exits with a non-zero code if any error is detected, therefore crashing the release pipeline as expected. The additional ISBN check can be enabled with the --ISBN flag, but requires the OBO document to parse successfully beforehand.

OBO Graphs Provisional Mapping

The BBOP team, as part of the GO project, is developing a more compact and developer-friendly way of exchanging ontological knowledge in the form of JSON-serialized graphs derived from one or more ontologies. This new interchange format, named OBO Graphs^a, reduces the ambiguity and the complexity of the exchanged data, while also removing the need for any dedicated parser, since JSON can be read by any of the regnant programming languages.

Some Python libraries, like ontobio^b, are using OBO Graphs as their internal data representation; but because the adoption is slow, they support loading OBO or OWL ontologies using an external converter like ROBOT, with the downside that it requires a Java runtime on the end-user machine.

Using the in-development schema, I developed a library declaring the OBO Graph data model, as well as JSON and YAML serialization/deserialization support derived with the serde Rust library. I then added translation mappings between OBO and OBO Graphs, replicating the current semantics of the OWL API, and made them available in the API of the Python module. Because the schema is under development, this personal take at the OBO Graphs format and interconversion led to proposing enhancements, such as the creation of new `SynonymType` and `Subset` node types^c.

a <https://github.com/geneontology/obographs>

b <https://github.com/biolink/ontobio>

c <https://github.com/geneontology/obographs/issues/46>

FastOBO Python Wrapper

While the ontological ecosystem revolves around Java, Python is one of the most popular languages for researchers, and in particular bioinformaticians. Because the lack of Python libraries for ontology usage end up slowing the adoption of ontologies by the less computer-savvy part of the community, I decided to make the parser and AST available as a compiled Python module using `pyo3` to derive the required CPython ABI^a. Rust being built on the LLVM^[21], it can easily compile to many different architectures.

Because Python does not support algebraic types like Rust does, the tree structure is slightly harder to model using Python classes. I used two complementary approaches to reduce the problem; firstly, Rust enums were translated into Python abstract classes, with one concrete class per enum variant. This makes pattern matching less elegant than with a proper enum type, but allows keeping the same typing hierarchy than the Rust one. Secondly, I provided a simpler way to check a clause type by simply checking its `raw_key` attribute instead. An example use-case, in the form of a simple traversal script, is shown in List.2.

```
>>> from urllib.request import urlopen
>>> import fastobo
>>> res = , stream=True)
>>> for frame in fastobo.load(urlopen("http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/cl.obo")):
...     for clause in frame:
...         if clause.raw_key == "def" and not clause.definition:
...             print("Empty definition of", frame.id)
```

Listing 2: An example Python script using `fastobo-py` to find frames with an empty definition clause in the current version of the Cell Ontology.

I also provided proper error wrapping so that error management in the Python module makes it easy to identify errors in invalid OBO documents. In particular, syntax errors use the builtin `SyntaxError` class to properly report the location of the error as well as the source document, if any. The name of the reported rules correspond to the production rules in the PEG grammar. An example syntax error raised by an older version of the Gene Ontology can be found in List.3.

The Python module makes it easy to load, edit and save OBO ontologies at the syntactic level, while benefiting from the Rust typing system. Performance-heavy operations such as ID compaction or decompaction can be called from the Python interface but are implemented in Rust for better performance. The API is heavily inspired by other parsing modules from the Python standard library, such as the `json.load` and `json.loads` functions.

a <https://docs.python.org/3/c-api/stable.html>

```

>>> import fastobo
>>> fastobo.load("go.obo")
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "<stdin>", line 1, in <module>
  File "go.obo", line 107377
    synonym: "ABC-type oligosaccharide transporter" EXACT [EC 7.5.2.2]LF
                                                    ^
SyntaxError: expected QuotedString

```

Listing 3: A Python `SyntaxError` raised when trying to parse the GO release in OBO format. Note that the error is spanned, and properly reports the column and line position of the error encountered by the parser.

fastobo-py is hosted on GitHub^a and can be downloaded as a precompiled Python wheel or built from source from PyPI^b under the MIT license. The dependencies management is carried out by Dependabot, while the continuous integration and release for multiple platforms is done with Travis-CI. Documentation built with Sphinx for the latest release can be found on ReadTheDocs^c.

OBO to OWL2 Restricted Mapping

Because OWL2 is the W3C recommended language for ontology edition and usage, most tools expect OWL-formatted ontologies as inputs. This is particularly true for reasoners such as Pellet^[22] or Fact++^[23] which are commonly used to infer new conclusions on ontology documents. Consequently, most of the OBO ontologies end up requiring a conversion from OBO to OWL eventually, when they are not consumed directly. While this is not needed for ontologies being developed in OWL such as CL, older ontologies like GO begin their lifetime as OBO files, only to be translated into OWL during the release process. Consequently, this translation must be as semantically-accurate as possible.

In order to support conversion outside of the Java world, I developed OBO to OWL mappings in an external crate, based on the OWL2 data model provided by the Horned-OWL library. This mapping, based on the OBO format version 1.4, requires a complete traversal of the knowledge graph generated by the OBO document and all of its imports. Developing this crate also helped identifying semantic errors in the working draft of the OBO 1.4 specification. Each frame is then processed independently to create a set of annotated axioms that are then injected into the resulting OWL ontology. The translation of a simple frame from the MS ontology^[24] is shown in List.4.

a <https://github.com/fastobo/fastobo-py>
b <https://pypi.org/project/fastobo>
c <https://fastobo.rtd.io>

a.

[Term]

id: MS:1000031

name: instrument model

def: "Instrument model name not including the vendor's name." [PSI:MS]

relationship: part_of MS:1000463 ! instrument

b.

```
Declaration(
  Class(<http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031>)
)
AnnotationAssertion(
  Annotation(
    <http://www.geneontology.org/formats/oboInOwl#hasDbXref>
    "PSI:MS"^^xsd:string
  )
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/IAO_0000115>
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031>
  "Instrument model name not including the vendor's name."^^xsd:string
)
AnnotationAssertion(
  <http://www.geneontology.org/formats/oboInOwl#hasOBONamespace>
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031>
  "MS"^^xsd:string
)
AnnotationAssertion(
  <http://www.geneontology.org/formats/oboInOwl#shorthand>
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031>
  "MS:1000031"^^xsd:string
)
AnnotationAssertion(
  rdfs:label
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031>
  "instrument model"^^xsd:string
)
SubClassOf(
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031>
  ObjectSomeValuesFrom(
    <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000050>
    <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000463>
  )
)
```

Listing 4: The OBO to OWL2 translation of a simple term frame from the MS ontology. **a.** The MS:1000031 term in OBO syntax. The document also contains a default_namespace header clause setting MS as the default prefix not shown in the listing. **b.** The resulting OWL2 axioms after translation, in OWL Functional syntax. Note that the oboInOwl:shorthand annotation is the correct way of adding CURIE to translated entities; the OWL API uses oboInOwl:id instead, which is actually undeclared.

The reverse mapping, however, was not developed because the OWL2 language is more expressive than the OBO language, and because this use-case is fairly limited. The translation couldn't be done on a low-level like the OBO to OWL translation, but would have required a pattern-matching approach to identify artefacts of OBO to OWL translation in order to translate them back into OBO.

a.

```
[Typedef]
id: adjacent_to
xref: RO:0002220
property_value: example_of_usage "... " xsd:string
  {http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#seeAlso="issuecomment-218584934"}
```

b.

```
AnnotationAssertion(
  Annotation(
    <http://www.geneontology.org/formats/oboInOwl#http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-
      schema#seeAlso>
    "issuecomment-218584934"^^xsd:string
  )
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/IAO_0000112>
  <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002220>
  "... "^^xsd:string
)
```

Listing 5: **a.** A typedef frame in the Core Ecological Entities ontology. The `id` clause of the typedef is used as a shortcut, and will be replaced by the `xref` identifier `RO:0002220` as per the ID translation rules of the OBO format. **b.** The invalid translation to OWL Functional produced by the OWL API. The translation is invalid for 2 reasons: on the syntactic level, the first IRI in the document is invalid, because it contains unescaped reserved characters in the path component; on the semantic level, the `rdfs:seeAlso` IRI should not be prefixed with the `oboInOwl` namespace, as the qualifier is already an URL identifier.

Formal OWL2 Functional Parser

Because the OBO format does not have sufficient power to express any OWL2 construct, it supports a special header clause `owl-axioms` to store untranslatable axioms in raw text. When adding such axioms to the OBO document header clause, they must be serialized using the OWL2 Functional syntax, like shown in List.4a. In order to process these axioms back when translating from OBO to OWL2, it was deemed necessary to write an OWL2 Functional syntax parser for the horned-owl library.

I used the same method as for the OBO parser, translating the context-free BNF grammar in the W3C recommendation into a PEG grammar derivable with pest. The tokenizer was much simpler to obtain, as the OWL2 Functional grammar is normative and unambiguous. I then wrote conversion traits to convert the token pairs into the Horned-OWL data structures, which required a context to be passed for IRI expansion.

During development of the OWL2 Functional syntax parser, an additional error^a was detected with the OWL API that involved invalid IRI expansion during translation from the OBO product of ECOCORE^[25] to an OWL Functional document. This error, presented in List.5, suggests a bug on both the syntactic and the semantic levels.

Furthermore, it was discovered that the current behaviour of the OWL API for `owl-axioms` translation was not the one described in the OBO specification: whereas the current standard is to wrap all axioms into a single OWL ontology declaration, the OWL API allowed complete ontology documents to be declared, including prefixes which have no semantic value. This behaviour is reflected in released ontologies such as MCO^[26], which uses the `owl-axioms` clause in an erroneous way. Since both behaviours however correspond to different production rules of the OWL2 Functional grammar, it is possible to handle both cases independently to extract the serialized axioms.

RDF/XML Parser

As shown previously, conversion of OBO documents requires a complete traversal of the dependency graphs created by an OBO file and its recursive imports. However, for interoperability reasons, OBO documents can only import other ontologies in their OWL form. Because the main interchange format for OWL ontologies on the OBO Foundry is the RDF/XML syntax of OWL2, it was necessary to provide a solution to parse this file format.

Looking at several Rust libraries for RDF revealed all of them were lacking RDF/XML parsing capabilities. Using the `quick-xml` Rust library, I developed an efficient parser of the RDF/XML file format for Sophia, a generic RDF library for Rust. Correctness was asserted using the W3C-provided test-cases^b. The parser was ultimately integrated to the Sophia source code^c and can be used since the 0.3.0 release of the library when compiling the source with the `xml` feature enabled.

a <https://github.com/owlcs/owlapi/issues/863>

b <https://github.com/w3c/rdf-tests/>

c https://github.com/pchampin/sophia_rs/pull/9

FastOBO Ecosystem

In conclusion, the Fig.3 shows the original implementations that were developed over the course of this project, as part of the ongoing effort to develop an efficient Rust stack for ontology edition, consumption and validation.

Figure 3: An overview of the ecosystem developed during this project. Arrows in blue indicate existing conversion utilities, typically found in the OWL API. Arrows in orange show libraries that were implemented over the course of this internship. Arrows in purple show other tools outside of the OWL API for which I contributed to the development of (either Sophia or Horned-OWL). Dashed arrows indicate a serialization or deserialization process (syntactic level), while plain arrows show a translation process (semantic level).

Methods

Technologies and Libraries

OWL Model

Horned-OWL^[27] is a Rust implementation of the OWL2 model written by Philip Lord to provide a faster and safer alternative to the OWL API. Still a work-in-progress, the 0.5.0 version was used throughout this project, as the most recent 0.6.0 features a lot of breaking changes that were not stabilised while the `fastobo-owl` and `horned-functional` libraries were being developed.

Ontology Development Kit

The Ontology Development Kit^[17] is a collection of tools to help with the development and releases of open-source ontologies being hosted on GitHub. The latest release 1.1.2 provides a Docker image with all tools required installed in the same place to improve the reproducibility of each build.

Parsers

`pest`^[28] is an open-source Rust library to derive tokenizers from PEG grammars, with additional checks at compile-time for grammar ambiguity. It was chosen over combinatory parser libraries such as `nom` because text-based formats are easier to parse using grammar-based parsers, and because an OBO grammar was already available. I also used `quick-xml`^[29], an XML parser with minimal memory footprint, and impressive performance; `xmlparser` would have been a better choice since it supports spans, but I was unaware of its existence when I started development.

The community-driven library `serde`^[30] is a framework to derive serializers and deserializers for Rust data types into many different formats, such as JSON, YAML, Protocol Buffers, or URL encoding. Stable version 1.0.0 was used throughout development.

PyO3

`PyO3`^[31] is a community-driven library providing macros to derive CPython-compatible code in Rust. It allows compiling native Python extensions from Rust code, inheriting its safety guarantees and execution speed. It is still unstable, but continuous integration allows safely updating to the latest version of the git repository between versions of `fastobo-py`.

Programming Languages

Rust is a strongly-typed, compiled, imperative language developed by the Mozilla foundation. It puts emphasis on program safety^[32], as well as on execution speed. The language features some abstractions borrowed from functional programming, such as algebraic types, or monadic error management. Bindings were provided from Python^[33] 3.5 and higher.

RDF Model

sophia^[34] is a generic Rust library for RDF triples and quads edition. Contrary to other RDF libraries, its entire API uses generic traits which makes it usable with any triple or quad store as long as they implement the required interface. The version 0.2.0 served as a base for the RDF/XML parser, which was then released as an optional feature of the version 0.3.0.

Software Engineering Practices

The following practices of software engineering were followed during the development of the fastobo ecosystem and derived tools.

Continuous Integration

Continuous Integration is the process of testing changes on a regular basis to create releases as early as possible. Although historically this term designated the act of making daily builds of a program (so-called *nightlies*, compiled during the night and inspected in the morning), its accepted signification is now the action of continuously testing the software against automated tests.

Semver

Semantic Versioning^[35], or semver for short, is a specification of release *tagging*, that eases computer understanding of what a **version number** is. It enforces a stable API between releases of the same major version, and helps managing dependencies of a software project, while avoiding cryptic version tags such as *v1.18-A.rc13.beta*.

UNIX Philosophy

Though no standard definition of it exist, computer scientists agree that the **Unix Philosophy**^[36] enforces simplicity and modularity. Programs that follow it (such as the GNU *coreutils*^[37]) tend to be designed in a way they perform only a single task, but can be used in combination with other programs. Development following this paradigm tends to produce small independent programs or libraries that once assembled perform well instead of creating a bulky program with many features.

Version Control

A **version control** system is a program that manages the whole history of a software project, as well as coordinating different developers working on the same project. **Git**^[38] (used in this project), Mercurial, or Subversion are the common ones.

Development Services

Software Forge

A software forge is a platform for collaborative development and sharing of open-source projects. Libraries described on this projects are all hosted on **GitHub**, under the FastOBO^a organisation account.

Travis-CI

We used **Travis-CI** as the continuous integration service for this project, because it supports both Python and Rust as computer programming languages, as well as OSX and Linux as operating systems.

Dependencies Management

Dependabot is used to monitor the dependencies of the various pieces of software developed during this project, bumping them and opening pull requests if needed. It serves a critical role in updating the unstable requirements of `fastobo-py`.

Documentation Hosting

ReadTheDocs and **Docs.rs** are documentation building and hosting websites for Python and Rust respectively. The first one uses **Sphinx**^[39] to build the documentation from reStructuredText documents, while the second one builds the documentation directly from Markdown snippets in the Rust source code of a library.

Release Hosting

Rust libraries developed during this project can be found on the Rust registry **crates.io**, which is the default hosting solution for Rust crates. Python releases of the `fastobo-py` module are available as Python wheels on **PyPI**. Binary releases of `fastobo-validator` can be found on **Bintray**, a binary repository manager that supports open-source projects in several release channels or archive formats.

a <https://github.com/orgs/fastobo>

Discussion

Issues with Import-processing

As shown on multiple occasions, translation from the OBO language into other ontology formats all require preliminary import processing. This currently cannot be done because the Horned-OWL library does not provide an OWL RDF/XML parser, which the format of OBO Foundry-hosted OWL ontologies. However writing a parser for the OWL RDF/XML format is a short-term goal of the Horned-OWL developer, so import processing will ultimately be integrated to the different translation processes. A much better solution however would be to get rid of import requirement, which is almost only required for the translation of relationship entity clauses, as described in depth in the next section.

Community Integration

The short-term goal of this project was to provide an open-source, efficient parser and conversion implementations for the OBO format, with community usage in mind to avoid the plague of artisanal parsers in projects consuming ontologies. In particular, *fastobo* is expected to become the native OBO parsing module for the *ontobio* library^a, part of the Monarch Initiative, as well as the default OBO parser for the *pronto* library, both of which are Python library for ontology consumption.

This project was presented during a flash-talk and as a poster^b during BOSC 2019, a track part of the ISMB/ECCB 2019 edition in Basel. During this conference, I engaged in several positive interactions, both with ontology developers, and with ontology users.

Finally, the integration of the validation binary to the ODK is expected to raise awareness of semantic correctness among ontology developers, in particular for curators who are still relying on older utilities such as *OboEdit*^[40] and do not know they are producing invalid files.

Towards OBO 2.0

Fixing the OBO format is not a simple task, because of its history as an *ad-hoc* format and the importance of the OWL API in the definition of its semantics. It also contains constructs that were useful for old use cases and that are now, if not deprecated, obscure at best.

a <https://github.com/biolink/ontobio/pull/360>

b https://www.iscb.org/cms_addon/conferences/ismbeccb2019/posters.php

While efforts look forward to embed OBO in OWL2, making OBO no more than an OWL2 syntax (such as the OWL2 RDF/XML, Functional or XML syntaxes), it currently has some bottlenecks to be considered as such. The most important one is the translation of the relationship entity clause, as it actually overloads several OWL2 constructs, because the resulting axiom is going to be context-sensitive, as partially shown in Eq.3.

$$\begin{aligned} & \top(\text{relationship: example_relation EX:001}) = \\ & \begin{cases} \text{ObjectHasValue}(\top(\text{example_relation}) \top(\text{EX:001})) & \text{if example_relation is class-level} \\ \text{ObjectSomeValuesFrom}(\top(\text{example_relation})\top(\text{EX:001})) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Equation 3: *Translation of a simple relationship clause into OWL2 axioms depending on a simple contextual property (is_class_level). Note that example_relation may not be declared in the current document but in one of its imports.*

In particular, the context required to accurately translate some clauses into the relevant OWL2 axiom can extend to the whole document, and, if that document contains imports, to the imported documents themselves. Therefore, the complete knowledge graph must be built before an OBO document can be translated, as opposed to other OWL2 syntaxes.

However, by using syntax to disambiguate between the different translation cases, we could eliminate the need for a context – or at least reduce it only to the current document. Doing so would be a breaking change, but would be a major improvement for OBO/OWL2 interoperability.

Spuriousness of the OWL API

Formalizing the OBO 1.4 language made it possible to identify numerous issues in the current OWL API. Although fixing them exceeded the scope of this project, some of them (such as the invalid IRI translation from OBO shown in List.4) were reported, but their patch is still pending. Other unreported errors include the translation of relationship clauses (as shown in Eq.3) that does not take import context into account, leading to invalid translation from OBO to OWL in some edge cases.

Before this internship was conducted, the OWL API was the only comprehensive implementation of the OBO format and of the OBO to OWL standard mapping; however, multiple errors were discovered during the few months of development. Given the prominence of the OWL API in the semantic biology community, this raises serious questions about the spuriousness of the produced products, in particular for large projects such as GO which release pipeline produces OWL2 using the OWL API internally.

Personal Experience

This project was started off my personal initiative, but the reason I chose to conduct it under the direction of **Chris Mungall** is thanks to his importance in the bio-ontology community. He was extremely helpful in getting me in touch with the right people, and my initial contact with **Phillip Lord** turned into a very pleasing collaboration that should give birth to a paper over the month of September. I also had the opportunity to meet **Matthew Horridge**, the main developer of the OWL-API and of the Protege editor^[41], during his visit to the LBNL. I used this limited time to discuss with him about some of the issues raised in this report, as well as about the general direction my work was taking.

Developing the **FastOBO** stack was my first large-scale project in Rust, which I had chosen because of several reasons, the most important of which being the typing system that I knew would help modelling the OBO syntax tree. I now consider myself almost as knowledgeable in Rust as I am in Python, with only half of practice time, and gained considerable confidence in my software development skills, in particular in the **devops** field.

Being at the centre of the **OBO ecosystem** also made me realise how **slowly** it was evolving: because it is composed of an intricate net of imports, some of which rely on outdated or deprecated ontologies, it can be very hard to get an upstream patch into a downstream release. Some of my patches took a month to be examined by the project developers, which is one of the reason I spent so much energy on **curation**, as I wanted to have as much errors as possible fixed. While I assume this to be the case with any large-scale software engineering project, I had the feeling this was especially true in the OBO community.

I was able to present this project during a poster session at the **BOSC** track of the 2019 **ISMB/ICCB** conference, which was incidentally my first poster session at a scientific conference. Over the course of the conference, I was able to discuss with people with whom I had interacted a lot online over the past few months, and also with people oblivious to the semantic biology field in the hope to get them interested. I also discussed with **Matúš Kalaš**, the lead developer of the EDAM^[42] ontology, about ontologies outside the OBO ecosystem, and the problems of interoperability with such ontologies.

Finally, it would be complete hypocrisy to pretend I did not enjoy the cultural environment of the city of Berkeley, and of the Bay Area in general. I am very satisfied with this internship overhaul; although I regret not having more time to improve this project even more, I don't think I would have changed anything in my way of working now that I see the final result.

Abbreviations

ABI	Application Binary Interface
API	Application Programming Interface
AST	Abstract Syntax Tree
BBOP	Berkeley Bioinformatics Open-source Projects
BOSC	Bioinformatics Open-Source Conference
BNF	Backus-Naur Form (Grammar)
BSPO	Biological Spatial Ontology
CL	Cell Ontology
ECCB	European Conference on Computational Biology
ECO	Evidence and Conclusion Ontology
ECOCORE	Ontology of Core Ecological Entities
GO	Gene Ontology
IRI	International Resource Identifier
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISMB	International Society for Computational Biology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JVM	Java Virtual Machine
LBNL	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
LLVM	Low-Level Virtual Machine
MS	Mass-Spectrometry (Ontology)
OBO	Open Biomedical Ontology
ODK	Ontology Development Kit
OWL	Ontology Web Language
PEG	Parsing Expression Grammar
PORO	Porifera Ontology
ROBOT	ROBOT is an OBO Tool
UBERON	Über-anatomy ontology
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

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